

ICT Access of Filipino Farmers in Capas, Tarlac

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I. INTRODUCTION

According to Heeks et al. (2003, p. 3), Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) can be viewed as tools to satisfy needs like “needs which improve access to the means of production and economic opportunities.” The 2019 report of *We Are Social*, 71% of Filipinos now have access to the internet using digital technologies. However, is the penetration of digitalization in our society reaches the marginalized sectors?

According to Philippine Statistics Authority, farmers are considered as poorest of the poor in our country (Philippine Daily Inquirer, 2017). How does it affect their access and use of ICTs?

This survey attempted to identify the digital devices that the farmers of a municipality in the Philippines, Capas, Tarlac, use. The study also looked into the frequency of usage and the problems they encounter while using the devices.

II. METHODOLOGY

The survey investigated the digital devices that the farmers use, the frequency of usage and their reason for using the devices. The participants are farmers from the municipality of Capas, Tarlac. A survey instrument in the form of a self-administered questionnaire was developed to accomplish the goals of this study.

The questionnaire contained 3 sections. In the first section, the participants checked the devices they have and the frequency of usage. The devices included in the study were

ICT Access of Filipino Farmers in Capas, Tarlac

partially based from the ICTs included in the list of Heeks et al. (2003) and these are: cellphone or smartphone, computer or laptop, television or smart TV, and option to add a device not included in the list. The second section got to know the respondents' purpose for using a particular device (communication, entertainment, information and work). And the last part asked the farmers to list down the problems they experience when using the devices. The questions were also translated to Kapampangan, a widely used language in the locale of the study.

The survey was completed by 20 farmers from two barangays in the municipality of Capas: Barangay Sto. Rosario and Barangay Lawy. Out of the 20 participants, 16 are males (80%) and 4 are females (20%).

After the survey, the results were tabulated to see the most popular device among farmers and to know the frequency of usage for each device. The purpose and the problems encountered while using the devices were also analyzed.

III. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The average age of the farmers in the survey is 45.3 years old which means most of the respondents fall under the majority age bracket of 25-54 years old of the agricultural labor force (Briones, 2017).

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, the basic ICTs for connectivity like phones are now more affordable and accessible to people in rural areas (Trendov et al., 2019). This statement from the report is reflected in the result of the survey because the most common device is cellphone or smartphone 75% of the respondents have this gadget. It is followed by TV / SmartTV, 10 respondents answered

ICT Access of Filipino Farmers in Capas, Tarlac

they own this digital device. Three farmers revealed that they own a tablet. The least popular is the laptop or computer; only one respondent owns this type of digital device.

Thirteen out of 15 farmers with cellphones reported that they use the device as means of communication and 12 answered they use it every day.

Nine out of 10 of farmers who own a television or a smart TV admitted that they use it every day. This result is not reflected on the next device on the list; two out of 3 tablet-users said they only use it 3-4 times a week. Lastly, the farmer who owns a computer said he uses it daily.

Communication is the top reason why farmers own these digital devices (65%). Half of the respondents said that they use their devices as sources of entertainment. Eight farmers said that that they get their information and news from the ICTs that they own. While 7 farmers claimed that these devices are useful for their jobs.

Regarding the problems they experience while using the devices, weak signal is the most common difficulty (55%) especially for owners of television and cellphones. The weak signal experienced by mobile users can be caused by lack of cell sites in the area. According to a report by Marasigan (2019), Philippines is one of the countries with the lowest number of unique physical cell sites in Asia. In fact, based on the Bandwidth and Signal Statistics of the Department of Information and Communications Technology (2018), there are only 105 detected 4G cell sites in Tarlac. On the other hand, TV-owners are still using antennas to get television reception

Another problem encountered by farmers is that they cannot charge while they are at work as reported by 4 farmers. This statement is supported by the fact that 13 million of

ICT Access of Filipino Farmers in Capas, Tarlac

the population are without electricity, and there is a lack of electricity access is greater in rural areas (Diaz, 2019).

Hardware problem that is experienced by 3 participants because of the age of their devices. Another problem encountered is language barrier. The 3 farmers who mentioned this difficulty admitted that sometimes they do not understand some words when they watch television. Two participants mentioned that they experience slow internet connection while using some of the devices.

Two farmers said they did not experience difficulty in using the device but the content affected their work in agriculture. According to the answer of one farmer, the news about rice tariffication law prompted 'palay' buyers to lower the price of their crops than the suggested price. This can be a subject of a new study.

Other problems that the farmers encountered are power outages and lack of mobile credits.

IV. CONCLUSION

According to the results of the survey, age did not play a role in a farmer's device preference.

Based on the paper by Bhattacharjee (2018), "use of ICTs in the developing economies is mostly limited to TV, radio mobile phones, and web portals" and this is reflected on the answers by the farmers from Capas, Tarlac.

ICT Access of Filipino Farmers in Capas, Tarlac

Of all the digital devices listed, phones are the most common devices that farmers have. The survey also found out that majority of farmers interacted with the digital devices they own every day.

The use of digital devices has an impact in the day to day lives of the farmers. Phones are now their means to socialize and communicate. Moreover, the farmers get their news and information relevant to them by using these gadgets. M K Pavan et al. (2019) claimed that ICTs help agriculture by improving information and communication processes. The digital devices also became part of their lives as sources of entertainment. Some respondents stated that these devices are now part of their work.

According to M K, Pavan et al. (2019), usage of ICTs is hindered by low service quality by providers and this is confirmed by answers of the farmers in this survey. Weak signal is still a problem in the municipality of Capas.

APPENDIX A- SURVEY INSTRUMENT FOR DEVC 202 TMA 2

EDAD:

KASARIAN:

OBRA/TRABAHO:

1. **Nanung ‘digital device’ ing atin ka? I-tsek king ‘table’ / Anong ‘digital device’ ang mayroon ka? I-tsek sa table.**
2. **Makananu me karalas gagamitan? I-tsek king ‘table’ / Gaano mo kadalas ginagamit? I-tsek sa table.**

Atin kung.../ Merong Akong...	Digital Device	Aldo-aldo /Araw-Araw	Apat o atlung beses kada domingo / 3-4 beses sa isang linggo	Minsan keng metung domingo / Isang beses sa isang linggo	Ali ke gagamitan/ Hindi ko ginagamit
	Cellphone/Smartphone				
	Laptop/Computer				
	TV/SmartTV				
	Aliwa Pa/ Iba pa:				

3. **Para nokarin me gagamitan? / Para saan mo siya ginagamit?**
 - Para makisabi/Komunikasyon
 - Libangan / Entertainment
 - Impormasyon, Balita
 - Obra/Work
 - Aliwa pa / Iba pa: _____

4. **Nanu la ring problemang araranasan mu kapag gagamitan me ing kekang ‘device’? / Anong mga nararanasan mong problema kapag ginagamit ang device?**

APPENDIX B- TABLES AND CHART OF RESULTS

	AGE	SEX	DEVICE	FREQUENCY OF USAGE	PURPOSE OF USING DEVICE				PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED USING THE DEVICES
					Communication	Entertainment	Information	Work	
1	47	M	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	None
			TV/SmartTV	Every day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Slow Internet Connection
2	55	M	TV/SmartTV	Every day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal, Power outage
3	60	M	TV/SmartTV	3-4 times a week	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal, Language Barrier
4	41	M	TV/SmartTV	Every day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal, Language Barrier
5	43	M	TV/SmartTV	Every day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal, No Mobile Load/Credit
6	41	F	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	None
7	55	M	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
8	65	M	Celphone/Smartphone	3-4 times a week	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal, Hardware problem, No Charging Outlets at Work
			TV/SmartTV	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hardware Problem (Touch Screen)
9	42	M	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
10	25	F	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
11	37	M	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
12	17	M	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	No Charging Outlets at Work
13	55	F	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No Charging Outlets at Work, Hardware problem
			Others: Tablet	3-4 times a week	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
14	32	M	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Framing of News Stories on TV affected local price of rice
15	28	F	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal, Slow Internet Connection
16	47	M	Celphone/Smartphone	Never uses it	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
			TV/SmartTV	Every day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal, Slow Internet Connection
17	64	M	TV/SmartTV	Every day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
18	54	M	TV/SmartTV	Every day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
			Others: Tablet	Every day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
			Celphone/Smartphone	Never uses it	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
19	48	M	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
			Others: Tablet	3-4 times a week	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weak Signal
20	51	M	Celphone/Smartphone	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Language Barrier, Framing of News Stories on TV affected local price of rice
			Laptop/Computer	Every day	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Language Barrier, Framing of News Stories on TV affected local price of rice
			TV/SmartTV	Every day	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Language Barrier, Framing of News Stories on TV affected local price of rice

Table 1. Results from the survey

ICT Access of Filipino Farmers in Capas, Tarlac

SEX		Number of Respondents			
Male		16			
Female		4			
DEVICE		Number of respondents			
		FREQUENCY OF USAGE			
		Everyday	3-4 times a week	Once a week	Never
Celphone/Smartphone	15	12	1	0	2
Laptop/Computer	1	1	0	0	0
TV/SmartTV	10	9	1	0	0
Others: Tablet	3	1	2	0	0
REASONS FOR USING DEVICE		Number of Respondents			
Communication		13			
Entertainment		10			
Information		8			
Work		7			
PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED		Number of Respondents			
Weak Signal		11			
Slow Internet Connection		2			
Hardware Problem		3			
No Charging Outlets at Work		4			
Language Barrier		3			
Framing of News Stories on TV affected local price of rice		2			
Power outage		1			
No Mobile Load/ Credit		1			
None		2			

Table 2. Summary of the Results

ICT Access of Filipino Farmers in Capas, Tarlac

Chart 1. Capas Farmer's Device Ownership and Frequency of Usage

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